

**TO STUDY THE NEED OF EDUCATIONAL GUIDANCE AND COUNSELING
STRATEGIES IN TEACHER TRAINING INSTITUTION**

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Abstract –

This research paper studies guidance and counseling strategies of trainee students. A study was delimited trainee students 182 were available at the time of teacher training result declared. A standardized questionnaire for teacher trainee containing 20 questions in professional guidance and counseling. Majority of trainee students were not having a knowledge of guidance, appreciating the self, appreciating others, appreciating home and family, Developing a sense of community, Making decisions and setting goals, - Understanding safety and survival, Understanding interaction between home, family, school and community, factors which affect school achievement. Finding implies the need for guidance and counseling strategies of trainee students

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Keywords –

Guidance and counseling strategies, trainee students, Decision Making, Teacher Training Institution, employee, Quality, Administration, environment, interaction between home, family, school and community.

Introduction-

One of the main functions of guidance and counseling at the teacher training level is to aid in the identification and development of the abilities and interests of trainee students. As a trainee student ascends to teacher training means higher levels of education. They realize they have a lot of skills and things to learn within a limited time. During this foundational stage

guidance and counseling is part of a teacher training programme. Guidance and counseling takes care of the trainee student's needs that cannot be met in a teacher training, such as microteaching, classroom teaching, seminars, school level internship. Guidance and counseling strategies helps these trainee students to understand their own strengths and limitations and to do scholastic work at the teacher training level of their ability, to gain information about future educational and vocational opportunities and requirements, to make realistic educational and vocational choices plans based on a consideration of all relevant factors and to find solutions to their problems of personal and social adjustment in the training institution and society.

Ministry of Education set up a Central Bureau of Educational and Vocational Guidance movement in the field of teacher training. Professional guidance on scientific lines started only in 1908 in Boston with the establishment of Parson's Vocational Bureau to help young generation to choose profession in accordance with their needs, interest and abilities.

Guidance and counseling is a universal and automatic phenomenon in the sense that every person who is more experienced than his counterpart endeavors to guide teacher students with regard to guidance and counseling, the results of the survey showed that teacher training counseling services, including psychosocial counseling, are crucial for proper adjustment of teacher students that were both directly and indirectly affected by the war.

Rath Strang “, Guidance is a process of helping the individual through his own efforts to discover and develop his potentialities in order to better adjust to the environment.”

Guidance and counseling is a process of knowing himself and relationship between teacher students and environment. Similarly, both trainee teachers and teacher students asserted that guidance courses and programs should be carried out to provide students with: opportunities to develop knowledge and appreciation of themselves. Opportunities to develop relationship skills, ethical standards and a sense of responsibility, opportunities to acquire skills and attitudes necessary to develop educational goals which are suited to their needs, interests and abilities. And finally information that would enable them to make decisions about life and career opportunities. The society is changing very fast today resulting into fast changing pattern of jobs and employment opportunities. The teacher student needs immediate information of various types at every step of training period. Such information can be supplied to teacher students by professional work in the field.

Objective of the Study-

1. To assist teacher students to make educational and vocational choices in order to built up a career.
2. To study the role of teacher educators in guidance and counseling strategies in teacher training institution.
3. To provide the necessary information to the teacher students about guidance and counseling strategies.

Research Design and Sample -

The teacher students result (B.Ed.) declared on May 2013. The researcher was taken trainee students 182 were available at the time of teacher training result declared. A standardize questionnaire for teacher trainee containing 20 questions in professional guidance and counseling. The study was conducted a survey method and collected a data for collection and qualitative analysis. There are 182 teacher students were available to collect data relevant to participation of teacher training institution (B. Ed.) of Kolhapur district. The questionnaires containing 20 were administered to teacher students randomly chosen from a cross section of the population.

The information trainee students 182 are given below.

Sr.No	Medium	Govt. institutions	Aided institutions	Non - Aided institutions	Total
1	Marathi	35	46	98	179
2	English	-	1	2	3
	Total	35	47	100	182

Analysis-

The teacher students result (B.Ed.) declared on May 2013. The researcher was taken trainee students 182 were available at the time of teacher training result declared. A standardized questionnaire for teacher trainee containing 20 questions in professional guidance and counseling.

The response of trainee students is given below.

Response	No. of trainee students	Percentage
Very poor	90	49.45
Poor	35	19.23
Average	32	17.59
Good	13	7.14
Superior	12	6.59
Total	182	100

1. 49.45% teacher students is different from others capacity, interest and tendencies. No trainee teacher guided to go to the direction of his needs, interest and capacities, teacher student might be fail in his efforts.
2. 19.23 % teacher students agree the society is changing very fast today resulting into fast changing pattern of jobs and employment opportunities. Teacher student's needs

immediate information can be supplied to him by professional counselor workers in the field.

3. 17.59 teacher students answers from economic point of view optimum utilization of resources is essential for optimum production and full employment in the educational filed.
4. 68.68% teacher students suggested guidance and counseling strategies for making proper adjustment of the individual in the society as much as for making the teacher students fully adjusted to the environment of teacher training institution.

The response of trainee students graph is given below

Observations –

Guidance and counseling strategies is to strengthen the teacher students by optimum development of his personality. Teacher students is not able to measure his strengths and weakness on his own and if efforts on to achieve a particular goal of life without knowing the capacity or interest, wastage of time, money and energy will be the result. The graph shows the maximum teacher students accept the need of guidance and counseling strategies.

Suggestions-

1. The training programme for teacher students should include familiarizing them with simple diagnostic testing and with problem of individual differences and the Implications of these differences for educational and vocational guidance practices.
2. There should be at least one teacher educator in the training institution who should be able to deal with the subject of principles of guidance and counseling strategies.
3. Guidance and counseling strategies should be introduced in the training institutions and in schools attached to the institutions so that the teacher students may get first-hand knowledge of the problems involved in educational and vocational development.
4. A minimum guidance and counseling strategies should be made available to all teacher training institutions by having one visiting located within a reasonable distance of one another and by allocating the simpler guidance functions to teacher students.
5. Programme for the development of guidance and counseling strategies literature, occupational information materials, films and filmstrips and psychological tests, need to be accelerated care being given to avoid duplication of efforts through increased communication among agencies working in these fields. Co-ordination of efforts should characterize all guidance and counseling programmes.
6. Teacher training institution should be assisted in providing hobbies and recreational activities as well as part-time employment opportunities for their teacher students. These should be organized in such a manner as to provide meaningful experiences for the teacher students, which will enable them to explore and develop their interests and abilities.
7. In addition to the training and extension programmes in guidance and counseling strategies mentioned earlier, emphasis should be laid research pertaining to guidance in the institution.

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